

Recently Recognised Breeds of Poultry and Duck by Nbagr Over Past Five Years

B.N. Patel M.V. Darji H.G Koladiya and AR Ahlawat

Department of Animal Genetics & Breeding

College of Veterinary Science & A.H.

Kamdhenu University, Anand

Introduction

Native chickens are a vital part of backyard or free-range farming systems in India. However, over time, their contribution to egg production has been declining. These chickens were historically neglected due to their lower production potential and were given minimal attention in breeding and development programs. A total of 20 breeds have been recognized and registered as native chicken breeds in the breed registry at ICAR-NBAGR (Indian Council of Agricultural Research - National Bureau of Animal Genetic Resources). Native chicken breeds in India are known for their resilience, thriving in challenging climatic conditions, and showing resistance to bacterial and parasitic diseases. Studies on these breeds under intensive farming systems have revealed high genetic diversity and unique traits that are often absent in improved or commercial breeds. This paper provides an overview of recently recognized native poultry breeds and their physical, economical characteristics, and ongoing improvement projects. It also discusses the challenges faced by the native chicken production sector in India.

Intensive poultry farming has seen significant growth in India, largely due to the increasing demand for broiler chicken and eggs. However, backyard poultry farming is still facing challenges due to lower productivity. One of the key reasons for this struggle is the lack of access to modern farming techniques, better breeds, and efficient resources. There is a high demand for indigenous chickens and eggs compared to broilers and layer eggs. This is because many people believe that the indigenous chicken has better taste, texture, and flavour. The local population values these characteristics, which have made indigenous chicken and eggs more popular in certain regions. Despite the advantages of indigenous poultry products, the low productivity in backyard farming makes it difficult for these farmers to meet the growing demand. To bridge this gap, it would be important to focus on improving the productivity of backyard poultry farms, while also recognizing and promoting the unique qualities of indigenous poultry. Providing better resources, training, and market access could help these farmers increase their output and tap into the high demand for indigenous products.

Table 1. New registered breeds/lines of poultry and duck

Sr No.	Species	Breed	Home tract	Year of registration	Accession number
1	Poultry	Pd2(vanaraja female)	Icar, Hyderabad	2020	INDIA_CHICKEN_001_PD2_13002
2	Poultry	Aravali	Gujarat	2023	INDIA_CHICKEN_0400_ARAVALI_12020.

3	Duck	Maithili	Bihar	2022	INDIA_DUCK_0300_MAITHILI_11002
4	Duck	Andamani	Andaman and nicobar	2023	INDIA_DUCK_3300_ANDAMANI_11003
5	Duck	Tripureswari	Tripura	2024	INDIA_DUCK_1900_TRIPURESWARI_11004

1. PD2 (Vanaraja female)

❖ Origin:

It has been developed by ICAR-Directorate of Poultry Research in Hyderabad and is an important female parent for the production of Vanaraja, a dual-purpose backyard chicken breed. It was derived from the SY-Multicoloured broiler control population, the PD-2 birds are known for their multicoloured plumage, single combs, and yellow skin and shanks. They are also characterized by brown eggs.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Body Weight and Shank Length:** At 6 weeks, the body weight of the birds ranges from 450-650 grams, and shank length ranges from 66-76 mm.
- **Adult Weight:** At 40 weeks, the females weigh between 2.4 to 2.8 kg, while males weigh between 3 to 3.5 kg.
- **Sexual Maturity:** The birds reach sexual maturity at an age range of 160 to 175 days.

❖ Economical Characteristics:

At 40 weeks, the egg weight ranges from 52 to 56 grams. The annual egg production is between 190 and 215 eggs. Approximately 5,000 birds are in the population. PD-2 line a robust and efficient source for breeding the Vanaraja chicken, which serves well for both meat and egg production in backyard farming systems.

2. Maithili ducks

❖ Origin:

The native origin of this breed is Bihar, and it is primarily distributed across districts such as Motihari, Sitamarhi, Madhubani, Araria, Kishanganj, and Katihar.

Female

Male

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Feather Color:** Light or dark brown feathers with a mosaic pattern (circular spots), dark brown to ash color in drakes.
- **Head Color:** Bright black or greenish-black in drakes, brown in ducks.
- **Body Carriage:** Slightly upright, with a horizontal bill shape.

These ducks are characterized by their uniform brown feathers, which may appear either light or dark, along with a distinct mosaic pattern created by circular spots on their feathers. In drakes (males), the color tends to be dark brown to ash, with a bright black or greenish-black head, while ducks (females) have a brown head.

❖ Economical Characteristics:

- **Age at First Egg:** The average age at which Maithili ducks begin laying eggs is 191.12 days, ranging from 159 to 223 days.
- **Egg Production:** On average, they produce 54.6 eggs annually, with the range being between 33 and 71 eggs.
- **Egg Weight:** The average egg weight is 49.53 grams.
- **Body Weight at 6 Months:** At six months, the body weight is typically 1.18 kg, with a range between 1.12 to 1.24 kg.
- **Population Size:** Approximately 46,000 ducks.

These ducks are particularly valued for their egg production and adaptability to the local environment.

3. Aravali

❖ Origin:

- The Aravali chicken is mainly found in the Banaskantha, Sabarkantha, Aravali, and Mahisagar district of Gujarat. This breed is known for its hardiness and adaptability to the harsh environmental conditions of the region, which includes extreme temperatures and limited resources. Aravali chickens are well-suited for free-range farming and are often raised in backyard systems.

❖ Physical Characteristics:

- **Plumage:** Male Aravali chickens have birchen plumage, while female have shafty and/or laced plumage.
- **Heat tolerance:** Aravali chickens have a high tolerance for heat.
- **Broodiness:** Aravali chickens are good brooders, with high hatchability and mothering ability.

❖ **Economical Characteristics:**

- Egg production: Aravali chickens produce an average of 72 eggs per year.
- Body weight: The average adult male body weight 1990 grams, while the average adult female weight 1618 grams.

4. Andaman duck

❖ **Origins:**

- The Andaman duck is medium sized, dual purpose duck breed.
- The Andaman duck is native to the Andaman and Nicobar Islands and is mainly found in the northern and central parts of the islands.

❖ **Physical Characteristics:**

- It has grey-brown to blackish brown plumage.
- The skin is a black and white band around the neck.
- It has a yellowish bill with a black tip.
- It has bright orange feet and blackish green or brown tail.
- It has longer neck than other indigenous ducks.
- It has shorter shank than other indigenous ducks.

5. Tripureswari Duck

❖ **Origins:**

The Tripureswari Duck is native to Tripura and is commonly found in districts such as Sepahijala, Gomati, Kowai, Dhalai, South Tripura, West Tripura, Unokoti, and North Tripura.

❖ **Physical Characteristics:**

- **Feathers:** A mix of colors, particularly dark brown plumage.
- **Head color:** green, black, white, grey, yellowish brown.
- **Bill, shanks, and feet:** Typically orange or yellow in color.
- **Weight:** By 12 months of age, they generally weigh around 1.199 kg.

❖ **Economical Characteristics:**

- This breed is primarily raised for both egg and meat production, making it a valuable resource for small-scale farmers.
- On average, Tripureswari Ducks produce eggs ranging from 70 to 101 eggs annually.